

Polarographic Studies on Mixed-ligand Complexes of Cadmium(II) with some Amino Acids (L-Leucine, DL-Serine or DL-Methionine) as Primary Ligands and 2,2'-Bipyridyl as Secondary Ligand

ZUBAIDA KHATOON and KABIR-UD-DIN*

Department of Chemistry, Aligarh Muslim University, Aligarh-202 002

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Polarographic studies on the binary Cd^{II}-AA/BP systems are many but none on the ternary Cd^{II}-AA-BP systems (AA=L-leucine, LE; DL-serine, SE; or DL-methionine, ME; BP=2,2'-bipyridyl). Our interest in the mixed-ligand complexes of metal ions with biologically significant ligands, prompted us to extend the work to study formation equilibria of the above binary and ternary systems.

Results and Discussion

Binary systems: The stability constants of binary complexes of Cd^{II} with AA and BP were determined separately under the conditions identical to those used for ternary systems. The reduction of Cd^{II}, both in absence and presence of ligands (AA or BP), was found to be reversible and diffusion-controlled. An increase in ligand concentration or pH shifted the $E_{1/2}$ of Cd^{II} to more negative values indicating complex formation. In case of AA as ligand, pH was adjusted with KOH and pH range of studies was 7.0–10.4. The complexation with BP was studied in the pH range 3.0–6.0 where the pH was adjusted with HNO₃. The concentration of unprotonated or free ligand was calculated from pH and the total analytical concentration using appropriate values of the protonation constants. Plots of $\Delta E_{1/2}$ vs log [X] for the systems were smooth curves indicating stepwise complex formations. Therefore, DeFord and Hume's method¹ was used to obtain the metal-ligand ratios and overall stability constants of the binary complexes. Graphical extrapolation method, developed by Leden, was adopted to obtain the β -values. $F_0(X)$, $F_1(X)$, $F_2(X)$... vs [X] plots, when extrapolated to [X]=0, gave the values of overall stability constants. In case of LE, SE and BP binary systems, the plot of $F_3(X)$ was horizontal to the x-axis indicating the formation of three complexes with Cd^{II}, viz. Cd(AA)⁺, Cd(AA)₂, Cd(AA)₃ and Cd(BP)²⁺, Cd(BP)₂⁺, Cd(BP)₃⁺. Likewise, formation of only two complexes were ascertained in Cd^{II}-ME binary systems as $F_2(X)$ vs [X] plot was parallel to the abscissa. The values of overall stability constants are recorded in Table 1. The values are in good agreement with literature data²⁻⁶ after allowing changes in experimental conditions.

The validity of the results (Table 1) was tested by applying the following criteria⁷

$$Y = \left| \frac{\sum \left(\frac{[F_0(X)]_{\text{expt}} - [F_0(X)]_{\text{calc}}}{[F_0(X)]_{\text{expt}}} \right)}{n'} \right| \quad (1)$$

where, $[F_0(X)]_{\text{expt}}$ is the value of $F_0(X)$ experimentally deduced from equation (2), $[F_0(X)]_{\text{calc}}$ is that obtained from equation $1 + \beta_{101}[X] + \beta_{102}[X]^2 + \dots$ and n' is the number of measurements,

$$F_0(X) = \text{antilog} \left\{ \frac{0.4343 nF}{RT} \Delta E_{1/2} + \log \frac{I_s}{I_c} \right\} \quad (2)$$

The values of Y (1.10%, LE; 3.65% SE; 1.02% ME; 1.47% BP) show that the results obtained by the graphic method are satisfactory⁷.

TABLE 1—STABILITY CONSTANTS OF BINARY AND TERNARY COMPLEXES OF Cd^{II}

System	l	n	m*	log β	
				Temp. = 35°, I=0.5 M (KNO ₃)	
				Present work	Lit. values
Cd ^{II} -LE	1	0	1	3.84	5.00 ^a
	1	0	2	6.32	7.30
	1	0	3	8.51	9.35
Cd ^{II} -SE	1	0	1	4.15	4.69, 4.00 ^{a,b}
	1	0	2	6.67	6.77, 7.15
	1	0	3	8.82	8.85, 9.22
Cd ^{II} -ME	1	0	1	3.78	3.81 ^c
	1	0	2	6.50	6.24
Cd ^{II} -BP	1	1	0	4.60	3.81 ^d
	1	2	0	7.30	8.00
	1	3	0	9.83	10.50
Cd ^{II} -LE-BP	1	1	1	7.15	3.93 ^e
	1	1	2	9.66	
	1	2	1	9.95	
Cd ^{II} -SE-BP	1	1	1	7.67	3.76 ^e
	1	1	2	9.84	
	1	2	1	10.04	
Cd ^{II} -ME-BP	1	1	1	7.37	3.89 ^e
	1	1	2	9.70	
	1	2	1	10.08	

*l, n, m are the stoichiometric coefficients corresponding to Cd^{II}, BP and AA, respectively. ^aRef. 2 (30°, 1.0 M). ^bRefs. 2 and 3 (25°, 0.5 M). ^cRef. 4 (30°, 1.0 M). ^dRef. 5 (25°, 0.1 M potentiometric values). ^eRef. 6 (30°, 0.2 M potentiometric values); values of log

$K_{\text{Cd(BP)}}^{\text{Cd(BP)}} / K_{\text{Cd(BP)}(\text{AA})}$ are quoted.

Ternary systems: For the ternary systems, [AA] was kept constant whereas [BP] was varied in the range (0.5–6.0) × 10⁻³ M (pH range: 8.5–9.5). When BP was added to the solution containing Cd^{II} and AA, the $E_{1/2}$ shifted to more negative values which were always greater than those observed for

single ligand systems. As reductions were polarographically reversible, equation (3), due to Schaap and McMasters⁸ modification of the DeFord and Hume method, was utilised at constant ionic strength to evaluate the overall stability constants of the mixed-ligand complexes,

$$F_{00}(\text{AA}, \text{BP}) = \text{antilog} \left\{ \frac{0.4343 nF}{RT} \Delta E_{1/2} + \frac{I_s}{I_c} \right\} \\ = A + B[\text{BP}] + C[\text{BP}]^2 \quad (3)$$

where,

$$A = 1 + \beta_{101}[\text{AA}^-] + \beta_{102}[\text{AA}^-]^2 + \beta_{103}[\text{AA}^-]^3 \\ B = \beta_{110} + \beta_{111}[\text{AA}^-] + \beta_{112}[\text{AA}^-]^2 \\ C = \beta_{120} + \beta_{121}[\text{AA}^-] \quad (4)$$

and β_{10m} and β_{1n0} are the respective stability constants of the binary complexes of Cd^{II} with AA and BP; β_{111} , β_{112} and β_{121} are the overall stability constants for the formation of ternary complexes $\text{Cd}(\text{AA})(\text{BP})^+$, $\text{Cd}(\text{AA})_2(\text{BP})$ and $\text{Cd}(\text{AA})(\text{BP})_2^+$, respectively. Table 1 records the overall stability constant values. The reliability of the method used was again tested on the basis of Y -values which ranged as following: 0.19–0.38% (LE), 0.52–3.78% (SE), 0.26–1.87% (ME).

The relative stabilities of mixed-ligand complexes can be quantitatively expressed in terms of $\Delta \log K$ values. $\Delta \log K_1$, for example, for equilibrium (5), is defined by relation (6),

$$\Delta \log K_1 = \log \beta_{111} - (\log \beta_{110} + \log \beta_{101}) \quad (6)$$

The statistical value of $\Delta \log K$ for coordination of two different bidentate ligands for an octahedral coordination sphere is $-0.4 \log K$ units⁹. The respective calculated values of $\Delta \log K$ (Table 2),

TABLE 2—VALUES OF $\Delta \log K$, $\log K_m$ AND $\log K_s$ FOR Cd^{II} -AA-BP SYSTEMS

Species	Temp. = 35°, $I=0.5$ M (KNO ₃) $\Delta \log K$	$\log K_m$	$\log K_s$
$\text{Cd}(\text{LE})(\text{BP})^+$	-1.29	0.34	0.04
$\text{Cd}(\text{LE})_2(\text{BP})$	-1.26	0.71	0.23
$\text{Cd}(\text{LE})(\text{BP})_2^+$	-1.19	0.56	0.08
$\text{Cd}(\text{SE})(\text{BP})^+$	-1.08	0.68	0.38
$\text{Cd}(\text{SE})_2(\text{BP})$	-1.43	0.68	0.21
$\text{Cd}(\text{SE})(\text{BP})_2^+$	-1.41	0.55	0.07
$\text{Cd}(\text{ME})(\text{BP})^+$	-1.01	0.47	0.17
$\text{Cd}(\text{ME})_2(\text{BP})$	-1.40	—	—
$\text{Cd}(\text{ME})(\text{BP})_2^+$	-1.00	—	—

for example, for 1:1:1 Cd^{II} -AA-BP complexes are -1.29, -1.08 and -1.01. Higher negative values of $\Delta \log K_1$ suggest that 1:1:1 mixed species are less stable than the simple 1:1 complexes (or formation of 1:1:1 species is not favoured according to equilibrium (5)). In other words, BP binds better to Cd^{II} than to the binary $\text{Cd}(\text{AA})^+$ complex. This is due to the fact that more coordination positions are available on Cd^{II} than on $\text{Cd}(\text{AA})^+$ complexes.

Relative stability of a mixed-ligand complex with respect to parent binary complexes can also be evaluated from the expression,

The mixing constant (K_m) is given by¹⁰,

$$K_m = [\text{Cd}(\text{AA})_m(\text{BP})_n] / [\text{Cd}(\text{AA})_p]^{m/p} [\text{Cd}(\text{BP})_p]^{n/p} \\ = \beta_{1nm} / \beta_{10p}^{m/p} \beta_{1p0}^{n/p} \quad (8)$$

or

$$\log K_m = \log \beta_{1nm} - 1/p (m \log \beta_{10p} + n \log \beta_{1p0}) \quad (9)$$

The stabilisation constant (K_s) for ligands of equal denticity is given by

$$\log K_s = \log K_m - \log (p/mn!) \quad (10)$$

The K_m and K_s values for 1:1:2 and 1:2:1 complexes with methione could not be calculated as the value of stability constant for $\text{Cd}(\text{ME})_3$ was not known. Calculated values of $\log K_m$ and $\log K_s$ for the ternary systems are listed in Table 2. All the K_m and K_s values are positive showing that 1:1:1 mixed complexes are relatively more stable than 1:2 binary complexes, and 1:1:2 and 1:2:1 ternary complexes are more stable than the corresponding 1:3 binary complexes. The stability order of 1:1:1 ternary complexes with respect to the primary ligand (AA) is $\text{LE} < \text{ME} < \text{SE}$.

Experimental

The ligands LE (Merck), SE (B.D.H.), ME (SISCO) and BP (AnalaR) were used as received. Preparation of stock solutions, source of other chemicals, instrumentation, experimental details, etc. have been described elsewhere¹¹. The protonation constants of the amino acids, determined according to Irving and Rossotti's procedure¹², were found to be $(\log) K_H$, 35°; $I=0.5$ M (KNO₃) 9.60 (LE), 9.00 (SE) and 9.06 (ME). For BP the values were taken from literature¹³ ($\log K_H^1 = 4.40$, $\log K_H^2 = 2.80$).

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